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Man at the Crossroads: the clash between the Rockefeller family and Mexican artist Diego Rivera in 1933

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ABSTRACT

In the late 1920s and 1930s, a rapprochement between the United States and Mexico occurred through the artistic movement of muralism, which was accompanied by an appreciation of Mexican culture and nationalist sentiments. The Rockefeller family, primarily associated with entrepreneurship, had begun to approach Latin American art and planned to include artists from around the world for their Rockefeller Center project, which focused on the importance and valorization of technological progress for the future of humanity. The commission of Diego Rivera to paint a mural in 1932, the inclusion of the portrait of Vladimir Lenin, and his refusal to remove it led to a conflict in 1933 that revealed the scope of free speech in art and the boundaries between the aesthetic and political significance of a work of art. The purpose of this paper is to explore the motives that led the Rockefellers to hire such a controversial and politically engaged figure as Diego Rivera –in an environment where socialist ideas were met with public disapproval– and the reasons why the artist accepted the commission, coming from a family that was the epitome of capitalism. Through the use of primary sources and scholarly literature and the application of a qualitative approach, this thesis argues that the vision that the Rockefeller family and Diego Rivera had for the mural was similar in terms of the role of technology in the development of human society. What was at odds, however, was the ideological standpoint from which each took the commission and their vision of the future society. Rivera was not willing to give up his political beliefs, and the Rockefellers believed that the artist could separate his political goals from the aesthetic project. The divergence was thus inevitable, but at the same time this episode served to reassure both sides of their importance in their respective contexts and to reflect on the paradoxes in the relationship between art interests and business advantages.

Keywords

Mexican muralism, Diego Rivera, Rockefeller family, Man at the Crossroads, Vladimir Lenin

Introduction

In the late 1920s and 1930s, Mexico and the United States developed a close relationship through the artistic movement of muralism, whose notable representatives include the names of Diego Rivera, José Clemente Orozco, and David Alfaro Siqueiros. North American dealers, businessmen, and art promoters were fascinated by these artistic figures, not only for their melancholy and nationalistic depictions of Mexico, but also for their charismatic personalities that eventually made them stars of more than one controversy. These artists were created in a hectic political scenario after the end of the Mexican Revolution, and therefore their artworks were not only tainted with the country's cultural heritage, but also with political meanings and social implications.

Mexican painter Diego Rivera is the epitome of a controversial man, both as an artist and as a person, constantly defying the status quo, presenting himself as a polemical personality and making his mark on the art world. His curious and adventurous life, his travels from Mexico to Europe, his shifting styles –from Cubism to Impressionism–made him a multifaceted artist, and his political background made him a controversial figure in the United States. Meanwhile, the wealthy Rockefeller family, known for its oil business and philanthropic involvement, was in the midst of building the infamous Rockefeller Center in New York City –from 1930 to 1939– and was seeking a number of artists willing to exhibit their work in the building's various facilities.

The recruitment of Diego Rivera led to several controversies before, during and after the "non-completion" of the fresco *Man at the Crossroads*. The reason was the ideological and political views of the artist, as well as the final drawings on the wall of the main building of the "Radio Corporation of America", which included a representation of the socialist leader Vladimir Lenin. The debacle ended with the destruction of the artwork and Rivera's reprisal at the Palace of Fine Arts of Mexico, where he reproduced the painting in 1934, confirming and reinforcing his previously censored vision in a work titled *Man, Controller of the Universe*.

The state of affairs thus raises many puzzles, which are the subject of this investigation. First of all, there is the question of what content the Rockefeller family wanted to portray, considering their particular taste in art and the main ideas of their project. This leads to a second question that focuses primarily on the other personality involved in the controversy, particularly with regard to the intentions or claims that Diego Rivera wanted to express with the project *Man at the Crossroads* for the Rockefeller Center, or more precisely, the consideration of what the aesthetic project was on the one hand and a political goal on the other hand. Finally, the third question concerns two aspects: first, it is important to understand the reason for Rivera's decision to introduce Lenin, why he so bluntly refused to remove him from the painting, and whether he had actually included the socialist leader in the sketches he had previously submitted to Nelson Rockefeller's advisors and to the magnate himself; and second, the answer to the question concerning the Rockefellers' reason for hiring Rivera, given the artist's political background.

This article, therefore, attempts to answer these questions by taking into account what has been developed so far by many scholars, as well as by analyzing numerous primary sources (such as newspaper articles and correspondence letters from the period) concerning not only the two main characters of this narrative –Nelson Rockefeller and Diego Rivera– but also other people involved in the historical fact. This analysis is carried out from a qualitative perspective, taking into account that this is a historical subject in which each event and fact cannot be detached from its own context and there is no absolute truth, but only an interpretation of the historical fact.

The Rockefeller family and the plans for the Radio Corporation of America Building

Rockefeller, a family name considered highly influential, leading and pioneering in the U.S., is primarily associated with the oil business and franchising, at a time when the United States was still in the process of becoming a major world power in the 19th century. “*To tell the manner of its making is to tell the story of the development of American business as we know it. It is to trace the evolution of the economic system under which American business now flourishes*”¹.

Before the episode with Diego Rivera, the Rockefeller family had never been spared scandal. The scattered image of the family as a single capitalist monster was not new, considering that it had been involved in several affairs that did not give it a particularly optimistic image. In his review of Ferdinand Lundberg's book entitled *The Rockefeller Syndrome*, journalist G. William Domhoff assessed that, despite what at first glance appeared to be a sensationalist account, it gave a clear idea of the fierce judgments made about the family. Lundberg distrusted the family's charitable work, which he attributed to an excessive Puritanism, and accused them of using people to gain additional political and economic power². To understand the Rockefeller family, however, one must realize that they were people of their time who were no strangers to the development of capitalism in times when the United States offered such business opportunities.

John D. Rockefeller Sr. was in the right place at the right time when machinery, railroads, the development of corporate finance, and the exploitation of natural resources were emerging in the United States. He began his ventures by founding several companies related to oil refining and transportation, the best known of which is *Standard Oil Company*, founded in 1870 to focus on the production of petroleum and its products. The first problems Rockefeller's immense fortune brought arose when he seemed to monopolize the entire oil industry. He faced antitrust laws and several lawsuits that eventually led to the breakup of his company in several other cases, regardless of the fact that his fortune remained intact³.

John D. Rockefeller Jr. is considered more conciliatory than his father. He came on the scene around 1897 to run the business after his father withdrew from the *Standard Oil Company*, although he already held the role

¹ John T. Flynn, *God's Gold: The story of Rockefeller and his times*, (New York: Harcourt, Brace and Company, 1932), 5.

² G. William Domhoff, "The Rockefeller Syndrome", *Libertarian Review* (1976): 1-5-6, <https://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.188.8233&rep=rep1&type=pdf>

³ Flynn, *God's Gold: The story of Rockefeller and his times*.

of president of the company. The family's name was again put in jeopardy after the Ludlow Massacres of 1913-1914, when the Colorado Fuel and Oil mining company took on the United Mine Workers, who demanded wage solutions and better working conditions. Rockefeller Jr. left the matter in the hands of his executives, who launched a particularly harsh repression against the workers; the armed conflict ended with dozens of people suffocating as they tried to save themselves. The incident brought bad publicity not only to Rockefeller Sr. who had already been indicted, but especially to Rockefeller Jr. since he was a member of the board⁴.

However, the main character in the episode of the clash with Diego Rivera in 1933 is Nelson Rockefeller, born of the marriage between Rockefeller Jr. and Abby Aldrich and considered the "rebellious son". His upbringing was primarily the responsibility of his mother, who spent much time introducing him to poetry, art and music. Nelson is said to have more of Aldrich in his personality than of Rockefeller and is described as an intuitive, organized, meticulous and talkative person⁵. During his college years, Nelson's interest in the arts developed, particularly in architecture, painting, and sculpture, and on a trip to Boston in 1930, he visited the Harvard Modern Art Society's exhibition of modern Mexican painters, which greatly impressed him and contributed to his art literacy. However, he never managed to convince his father of the importance of abstract art⁶, a peculiarity that was to be his undoing when he had to face the Rockefeller Center debacle. From these descriptions we can understand how committed he was to his goals and how this quality would certainly influence the way he dealt with the controversies in his life.

In the 1930s, the family name undoubtedly had a resounding impact on the American cultural scenario, after Rockefeller Jr. designed a major multipurpose complex that was emulated in various urban developments. *“While of John D. Rockefeller father it could be said he was the most important architect of the whole world oil industry, of his son we might say he would transform the design and development of commercial architecture around the world as a result of his multiple international entrepreneurs”*⁷. Rockefeller Center in New York, also known as Rockefeller City because of its ambitious background and location, is a bastion of economic development and a cultural symbol of an era marked by overcoming crisis and depression. The complex included thousands of square meters of space for offices, a cinema and separate buildings for international and commercial delegations, as well as residences⁸. *“Rockefeller Center is the heart of the culture industry on the east coast, and it was built at a moment when that industry was preparing for a major expansion into the new area of television (...). In addition to a real estate investment, and an investment in*

⁴ Ib.

⁵ Joe Alex Morris, *Nelson Rockefeller: A Biography*, (New York: Harper and Brothers, 1960).

⁶ Ib.

⁷ *“Mientras que de John D. Rockefeller padre podría decirse que fue el arquitecto más importante de toda la industria mundial del petróleo, de su hijo podríamos decir que transformaría el diseño y el desarrollo de la arquitectura comercial por todo el mundo como resultado de sus múltiples aventuras empresariales internacionales”*. Evan R. Ward, "Los Rockefeller: Arquitectos del Imaginario del Consumidor Latinoamericano", *RA: Revista Arquitectura*, (2006): 67.

⁸ Ib.

the emerging mass culture of America, Rockefeller Center was also an opportunity to cement ties with international business"⁹.

As mentioned above, the artistic-inclined side of the Rockefeller family was always attributed to Abby Aldrich and her fascination with Latin American, African, modern European, and folk art, which resulted in her participation in the foundation of the Museum of Modern Art (MoMA) in 1929, also part of the Rockefeller Center. The catalyst for the establishment of the museum was the lack of interest in the Metropolitan Museum of Art displayed in avant-garde art, as well as Pre-Columbian art¹⁰. In these years, the family experimented with arts patronage –according to Peter Collier and David Horowitz as a result of concerns regarding the threat to nationalize the Mexican oil industry¹¹– by signing artists such as Diego Rivera, José Clemente Orozco y David Alfaro Siqueiros, the ultimate representatives of Mexican *muralism*¹².

This appeal towards Latin American art has been also attributed to the Rockefeller's interest in joining the venture of allowing the United States to safeguard its leverage in the region, which will especially strengthen in the years during and after the Second World War¹³. Nonetheless, such drive had its origin in the 1930s, after Adolf Hitler and his party rose to power in 1933, and Latin America was being politically shaken from the core with the Nicaraguan rebellion which ended with the death of its leader Augusto Sandino and the arrival of populist leaders in Mexico and Brazil¹⁴. This interest in Latin American art could be therefore understood as the Rockefeller's contribution to the institutionalization, from the cultural and artistic perspective, of the influence of the United States over Latin America, particularly given the *transnationalization* of ideas that could pose socialism and communism as a threat to such control. This set of ideas which clashed with how the U.S. viewed the world from the political, economic, and cultural point of view, gave way to the implementation of a more soft power device that guaranteed that it could also monitor the artistic manifestations emerging from the Latin American region.

In this scenario, the project runners of the Rockefeller Center initiated their challenging task of finding the appropriate artists to take part in the decorative schemes intended for the building. The close relationship of Rivera with the Rockefeller family led to the assignment, around September and October of 1932, of a mural that would decorate Building No. 1 of the Rockefeller Center –Radio City Hall, also known as Radio Corporation of America, in the emplacement of the present 30 Rockefeller Plaza–. Rivera arranged to do a

⁹ Robert Linsley, "Utopia will not be televised: Rivera at Rockefeller Center", *Oxford Art Journal*, (1994): 49.

¹⁰ Alisa LaGamma, "The Nelson Á. Rockefeller Vision: In Pursuit of the Best in the Arts of Africa, Oceania, and the Americas", *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin*, (2014): 4-17.

¹¹ Linsley, "Utopia will not be televised: Rivera at Rockefeller Center".

¹² Patricio Del Real, *Building a Continent: the idea of Latin American Architecture in the Early Postwar*, Doctoral Thesis, (New York: Columbia University, 2012).

¹³ This idea is put forward by Helen Franc, "Early Years of the International Program and Council", *The Museum of Modern Art at Mid-Century: At Home and Abroad, Studies in Modern Art*, (1994), quoted by Kaziewicz, Julia, *Artful Manipulation: The Rockefeller Family and Cold War America*, Doctoral Thesis, (Williamsburg: College of William and Mary, 2015).

¹⁴ Irene Herner, "Diego Rivera. La búsqueda del paraíso proletario", *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Políticas y Sociales*, (2019): 180-185.

fresco mural after presenting a preliminary sketch, given the interest he had awoken in Nelson Rockefeller and his mother¹⁵.

Despite always having Rivera in mind, it seems that he was not considered “the main star” of the whole project by Rockefeller Jr., contrary to his son who held Rivera in high esteem. In a letter dated October 12th, 1932 from John Rockefeller to Raymond Hood, one of the project managers who traveled to Europe in search of highly renowned artists to take part in the Center, he regrets the fact that they couldn’t get Henri Matisse or Pablo Picasso, and refers to Rivera as follows: “*although I do not personally care for much of his work, he seems to have become very popular just now and will probably be a good drawing card*”¹⁶. On the other hand, regarding the same matter, Nelson Rockefeller asserted: “*I can’t tell you how pleased we all are that Rivera is going to do the art panel for the entrance of No. 1 building at Rockefeller Center. I feel this is perhaps the most important piece in the development and that he is, without question, the man to do it*”¹⁷. Therefore, Nelson was the promoter in the choice for Diego Rivera¹⁸, probably even before Rockefeller Jr. was contemplating the alternatives. And, as a result of their written expressions, it is possible to grasp the significance that each granted the Mexican muralist: John D. Rockefeller Jr. regarded Rivera as popular but not that much interesting, and Nelson was fascinated by his work and considered he was the only person who could fulfill the assignment.

Nonetheless, there was also an aesthetic fascination with Mexican art¹⁹, which was present not only in Nelson Rockefeller but also in his mother, Abigail. Rockefeller Jr. probably found it difficult to oppose both his wife and son’s wishes in entrusting the job to Rivera, especially when the everyday decisions were entitled to Nelson, and Rockefeller Jr. only intervened when affairs got excessively intricate, as happened later on.

Professor Michael Pupin, Serbian American physicist known for his work on telecommunications, sent the first proposal to John D. Rockefeller Jr. with suggestions for the different buildings in the Center in 1932. He regards the fact that the theme of the artistic adornment of the Rockefeller City had to ensure *the “significance, consistency and consecutiveness in the placing and subject-matter of the ornament...”* as well as “*characterize for public understanding the motives and purposes embodied in the enterprise*”²⁰. Even though the resulting entire setting wouldn’t be in line with each specific idea he proposed (he had even suggested Diego Rivera handle Building No.9), the idea as a whole remained prevalent: man as a builder, *Homo Faber*,

¹⁵ Morris, *Nelson Rockefeller: A Biography*.

¹⁶ John D. Rockefeller Jr. to Raymond Hood, October 12th, 1932, Rockefeller Archive Center, <https://storage.rockarch.org/a3458647-f426-46e3-8806-e3ca452e5d1f-5dc488af6eab4abdb2ded6bfa6b50cac.pdf>, (accessed on June 2020)

¹⁷ Nelson Rockefeller to Clifford Wright, September 23rd, 1932, Rockefeller Archive Center, <https://storage.rockarch.org/a3458647-f426-46e3-8806-e3ca452e5d1f-5dc488af6eab4abdb2ded6bfa6b50cac.pdf>, (accessed on June 2020)

¹⁸ Joanne Pillsbury, "The Pan-American: Nelson Rockefeller and the Arts of Ancient Latin America", *The Metropolitan Museum of Art Bulletin*, (2014): 18-27.

¹⁹ Margarita Nieto, "The Mexican presence in the United States: part I", *Latin American Art Magazine*, (1990): 28-34.

²⁰ Michael I. Pupin to John D. Rockefeller Jr., March 21st, 1932, Rockefeller Archive Center, <https://storage.rockarch.org/a3458647-f426-46e3-8806-e3ca452e5d1f-5dc488af6eab4abdb2ded6bfa6b50cac.pdf>, (accessed on June 2020)

and the great industries under the use of technology and communication. He regarded the fact that the theme should present Rockefeller City as a unique architectural monument as well as a social enterprise²¹.

In a memorandum dated March 1932 George Vincent, second President of the Rockefeller Foundation, sociologist, and dean in the University of Chicago of the College of Arts, Literature, and Science, follows some ideas previously proposed by Professor Pupin for the Rockefeller Center, and adds the notion that the Center should focus on the contemporary world. In Vincent's decorative scheme, certain aspects should be highlighted since they consist of warnings and can be widely applied to the subsequent controversy: he asserts there are certain limitations. In point c he states "*the idea of progress or evolution or the march of events can be represented only by contrasting past and present. This has been done so frequently that it has become conventional, even commonplace*"²². In point d, Vincent stresses that "*artists of high rank are likely to propose units intrinsically effective and beautiful which will not fit into any but the vaguest scheme. It would be unfortunate to give commissions not to independently imaginative artists but only to docile scene painters*"²³. Somehow, he was agreeing that only taking into consideration renowned artists could have its negative side because the principle should be conformity with the decorative scheme.

There are numerous letters between John D. Rockefeller Jr. and his advisers, in which many artistic names are juggled in consideration for the *Rockefeller City* project, such as Catalan muralist Josep Maria Sert and American painter and sculptor Maurice Sterne. Nonetheless, it is noteworthy that the name of Diego Rivera is mostly never mentioned as a novel feature: each time he is brought up in correspondence, he seems to be already considered as part of the project. This highlights how secure Nelson Rockefeller was with his choice, assuming Rivera's participation as a given fact.

There is also another aspect that goes beyond politically correct assumptions. Both Henri Matisse and Pablo Picasso had rejected the commission. If we analyze through the logic applied by Rockefeller Jr., the "most appealing" artists had declined, and even though Rivera was held in high esteem by Nelson and Abigail—who actually appreciated his work—what other choice did the magnate have than remain with the one man who had agreed to fulfill the task? At the same time, Nelson's predilection for Rivera's work must have been a defining issue, given that at the end of the day the artistic decisions were placed in his hands.

Diego Rivera, a man at a crossroad

To understand the intentions behind the mural painting *Man at the Crossroads*, we must fully grasp the context in which Rivera cultivated his artistic stamp. In the 1920s Mexico was going through the process of recovery from the intense years of Revolution, and one of the areas deeply impacted had been education—90% of

²¹ *Ib.*

²² Memorandum by George Vincent, March 1932, Rockefeller Archive Center, <https://storage.rockarch.org/a3458647-f426-46e3-8806-e3ca452e5d1f-5dc488af6eab4abdb2ded6bfa6b50cac.pdf>, (accessed on June 2020)

²³ *Ib.*

illiteracy rate—, for which José Vasconcelos, Minister of Education, launched a campaign of public education that included a mural program to educate the masses on Mexican history. *Muralism* allowed common people to gain knowledge about their own culture and society, but also to be in contact with spectacular works of art that exposed many great talents to the world²⁴.

Throughout his artistic education in Europe, and particularly from 1907 to 1910, the political socialist seed was planted in Diego Rivera after having read Karl Marx's writings and through his encounters with Russian exiles in Paris. In such environments, he began to develop a deep interest in social issues, and once he returned to Mexico in 1921, alongside fellow artists David Alfaro Siqueiros, Carlos Mérida, Amado de la Cueva, and others, he established the *Sindicato Revolucionario de Obreros Técnicos y Plásticos* (Technical and Plastic Workers Revolutionary Union), a community which aimed, through *muralism*, at perpetuating socialist ideas²⁵. The goal of this kind of art was to educate the Mexican society, aiming at the creation of a Mexican national identity, for which most of the themes revolved around the representation of Mexican history²⁶.

Thus, Rivera joined the Communist Party in 1922, becoming a member of the Executive Committee rather soon and using the newspaper *El Machete* to perpetuate communist ideology. However, in September 1929 he was expelled from the Party on the charges of “disobedience to its policies”, but also accused of being a counterrevolutionary and sympathizer of Mexican and American capitalists²⁷. This was deeply connected to the several commissions Rivera received from art representatives from the United States. Linda Bank Downs states that “*In accordance with the founding manifesto of the artists' union, Rivera painted his murals for an average worker's salary. But contrary to the spirit of this manifesto, he also accepted commissions from private collectors, for which he received considerable sums of money. For this 'treason' he was heavily criticized by his communist friends and colleagues*”²⁸. He was deemed hypocritical by the members of the Party since in 1928 he had completed the frescos for the Ministry of Education in Mexico and included cartoonish and mockery versions of John D. Rockefeller and Henry Ford, and especially because “*Rivera's feelings about American capitalism were not entirely negative; he believed that the new productive forces released in modern industry would bring about a better world*”²⁹.

As a result, Rivera was not only attacked from the right but also from the left in Mexico, given his flirtation with the leftist opposition embodied in Leon Trotsky³⁰. Diego Rivera's first encounter with *Trotskyism* took place during his trip to the Soviet Union from September 1927 to June 1928, where he witnessed the criticisms made against *Stalinism*. The main confrontation between these two conceptions of socialism was centered on

²⁴ Aguilar-Moreno and Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*.

²⁵ *Ib.*

²⁶ Jacinto Quirarte, "Mexican and Mexican American Artists in the United States: 1920-1970", in *The Latin American Spirit: Art and Artists in the United States 1920-1970*, by Luis R. Cancel, et al., 14-71, (New York: The Bronx Museum of the Arts in association with Harry N. Abrams, Inc., Publishers, 1988).

²⁷ Aguilar-Moreno and Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*.

²⁸ Joes Segal, "Between Nationalism and Communism: Diego Rivera and Mexican Muralism", in *Art and Politics: Between Purity and Propaganda*, by Joes Segal, 31-44, (Nieuwe Prinsengracht: Amsterdam University Press, 2015), 35.

²⁹ Linsley, "Utopia will not be televised: Rivera at Rockefeller Center", 48.

³⁰ Alex Goodall, "The Battle of Detroit and Anti-Communism in the Depression Era", *The Historical Journal*, (2008): 457-480.

Trotsky's vision of "international and permanent revolution", opposed to Stalin's idea of "socialism in one country"³¹. Rivera's measured proclivity towards *Trotskyism* and his distancing from *Stalinism* also awarded him the epithet of traitor to communism.

After being commissioned to paint murals in the United States, Diego Rivera, accompanied by his wife Frida Kahlo, arrived in the North American country in 1930, where he received a welcoming that was far from friendly: journalistic articles viewed him as a contentious figure, considered him inferior to the many prominent American artists, and a communist who instead of focusing on portraying the poverty of his nation was devoted to political propaganda³². According to Quirarte, the reactions towards the work of Diego Rivera in the U.S., as well as to his Mexican equals, reflected the existing xenophobia and paranoia, especially taking into consideration that it was supposed to open the path for American artists³³.

In 1930 Mexican newspaper *El Universal* argued that Rivera didn't take the protests seriously and that he even considered that his challengers lacked a sense of humor and common sense. In a statement to the edition, he is said to have acknowledged he was not a communist given his previous expulsion from the party and the persecution committed against him, and he also stated that he would continue to dedicate to his artistic labor³⁴. It is interesting to notice the departure he makes from the political institution of communism which, in my opinion, in no way implies his deviation from the ideology. This is well proven in the fact that he continued representing his political stand in his following pieces. By this account, it is not necessary to officially belong to a party to follow a specific political view. What Rivera did was continue being authentic to his ideals while not identifying purely as a communist from the institutional point of view during these times. According to his own words in 1932, he was a guerrilla fighter whose munitions didn't derive from the Communist Party, but from walls and colors. "*The guerilla fighter (...) whether important or insignificant, his action is always within the revolutionary line*"³⁵.

Both in the Detroit mural and the one for the Rockefeller Center, Rivera depicted his vision of technology used to benefit humankind, mastered as a tool to surpass the capitalist world and advance to a fairer society. He "*had a fascination for modern technology and industry, and believed that the machine would eventually contribute to the realization of a classless society*"³⁶. His writings in *The Revolutionary Spirit in Modern Art* can clarify any doubts about his political intentions through his art. There, he addresses terms such as "social classes" and "class-consciousness", making differentiation between bourgeois, revolutionary, and peasant art, and asserting that a proletariat art will emerge once the revolution fulfills its objectives and a classless society is installed. In his regard to artists such as Daumier and Courbet in the 19th century, while specifying that no

³¹ Dora Apel, "Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural", *Left History*, (1999): 57-75.

³² Aguilar-Moreno and Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*.

³³ Quirarte, "Mexican and Mexican American Artists in the United States: 1920-1970".

³⁴ "Diego Rivera no toma en serio la protesta: Decorará, por lo tanto, la Bolsa de Valores de los Ángeles, California", *El Universal: El gran diario de México*, September 25th, 1930.

³⁵ Diego Rivera, "The Revolutionary Spirit in Modern Art", *The Modern Quarterly*, (1932): 51-57.

³⁶ Segal, "Between Nationalism and Communism: Diego Rivera and Mexican Muralism", 40.

matter the social class from which they emerged the real relevance comes in the revolutionary spirit of their art, he reveals his non-condemning attitude towards bourgeois personalities³⁷. As a result, we can state that perhaps his travels to the United States and getting acquainted with liberal figures such as the Rockefellers or the Fords embodied his intention of promoting such social and political changes, instead of standing from a position of criticism, rejection, and confrontation. In a scenario like this, he could have been misconstrued, when he was actually implementing a somewhat conciliatory approach.

He also emphasizes, in line with his preceding outlook, that mural painting is the most important art for the proletariat, inspired also by the examples of the Soviet Union and the art displayed on the walls of Russia³⁸. By criticizing the colonial rulers and the United States' rejection of ancient art tradition in Mexico, we can once again envision his intention to defend and become the representative of Latin American art in the North American country. He might have taken it as a task to enlighten their minds with the kind of art he considered most authentic and socially engaged, as the par excellence tool for communist thinking.

Regarding the condemnation of being a propagandistic artist, he claimed that *"All painters have been propagandists or else they have not been painters (...). Every artist who has been worth anything in art has been such a propagandist"*³⁹. He then continued asserting that the accusation that propaganda damaged art had its foundation in bourgeois prejudice, in the fact that they preferred not to see art being used for the sake of the revolution. The bourgeoisie *"...does not want ideals in art because its own ideals cannot any longer serve as artistic inspiration. It does not want feelings because its own feelings cannot any longer serve as artistic inspiration"*⁴⁰. In his own words, Rivera wished to be a propagandist of Communism, using his art as a weapon. According to Joes Segal, Rivera considered that *"when the painter is a revolutionary, he will produce revolutionary art, no matter the circumstances and the character of his commissions"*⁴¹. The aforementioned scholar also addresses Alicia Azuela's conception when he asserts that *"Rivera felt the need to account for his acceptance of these commissions. He stated that an artwork can be meaningful to the proletariat even if it is paid for by a capitalist"*⁴². Therefore, the end justified the means.

While working on the mural for the Detroit Institute of Art, Rivera received Raymond Hood, who invited him to submit a draft alongside Pablo Picasso and Henri Matisse. Rivera rejected the commission right away given he considered his career was at a level in which competitions didn't favor his image, but eventually agreed. There, the intervention of Nelson Rockefeller was crucial after he demanded he wanted to be allowed to paint a colorful and narrative picture. Rivera started to work on the mural in March 1933, with assistants such as Ben Shahn, Lucienne Bloch, and Antonio Sánchez Flores⁴³.

³⁷ Rivera, "The Revolutionary Spirit in Modern Art".

³⁸ *Ib.*

³⁹ *Ib.*, 57.

⁴⁰ *Ib.*, 57.

⁴¹ Segal, "Between Nationalism and Communism: Diego Rivera and Mexican Muralism", 34.

⁴² *Ib.*, 39-40.

⁴³ Aguilar-Moreno and Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*.

Hence, in terms of the aesthetic project, if one observes the RCA mural, at first glance is possible to view “*a richly interconnected multi-space, multi-time composition drawing together all levels of human knowledge and existence –nature, science, industry, social and political life – based on axial dualities*”⁴⁴. In the artistic evaluations of *Man at the Crossroads*, one can find analyses that not only include the destroyed segment but also the ideas that Rivera later included in *Man, controller of the Universe*. To highlight the most important features, the left part represented the capitalist world throughout human evolution. This side of the wall also depicted war and violence, but with the idea that humankind is capable of enlightenment when it controls the forces of nature by creating science and technology as well. It is possible to view Charles Darwin embodying his theory of evolution, and poor people being repressed while the bourgeoisie laughs and seems delighted. The statue of Caesar has its head intact, while on the other side the head has been removed which symbolizes the end of tyranny⁴⁵. The right side portrayed the socialist world, where it was possible to see the masses defending civil rights. This is the side that generated the harshest criticisms, due to the inclusion of the face of Vladimir Lenin, who is holding hands with a black American and a white Russian soldier. “*The left wall portrayed human intelligence in possession of the forces of nature; the right wall showed the workers in control of society after the overthrow of tyrannical rule*”⁴⁶.

In the center there is a man who appears to be a peasant transforming the raw materials through science and technology; he is the main figure of the whole segment. Therefore, the role that Rivera granted the common people is reflected, as the main protagonists in his world paradigm. Above the man, there is a large cylinder as a telescope and below, two visual fields that represent ellipses crossed in the center, revealing biological and cosmic symbols referring to capitalist and socialist society⁴⁷. On the former is possible to view the moon, a dead planet, and the eclipse of the sun, as well as samples of diseases. On the latter, there is in the higher segment constellations and the planet Mars, and in the lower, a mass of dark cancer cells which, according to Rivera, were the cancerous cells of *Stalinism* contaminating the positive side⁴⁸. “*Rivera’s picture of an electrified cosmos is his endorsement of a Leninist faith in the necessary unity of technological and social change. As an associate of Trotsky, Rivera would naturally lay claim to an authentic Leninism, in opposition to Stalin’s encouragement of the cult of Lenin as legitimation for his own power*”⁴⁹.

According to his assistant Lucienne Bloch, Rivera chose to include Lenin because he considered him the true symbol of Communism as opposed to Stalin, whom he considered false and hazardous to Communism; his other assistant Ben Shahn suggested that Rivera did it to gain positive feedback from his former comrades in

⁴⁴ Apel, "Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural", 59.

⁴⁵ Aguilar-Moreno and Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*.

⁴⁶ Apel, "Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural", 60.

⁴⁷ *Ib.*

⁴⁸ Linsley, "Utopia will not be televised: Rivera at Rockefeller Center".

⁴⁹ *Ib.*, 53.

the Communist Party, who had accused him of being the “painter for millionaires”⁵⁰. In line with this insight, “*A need to assert his socialist credentials against accusations that he was a capitalist pet must have played a part in determining a choice of imagery for the Radio City that his patrons would certainly have found hard to accept (...)*”⁵¹. By the same token, “*Rivera’s efforts to assert his political integrity and simultaneously maintain artistic independence had the greatest impact on the iconography of his RCA mural, culminating in the recreated mural in Mexico City*”⁵². As a result, we can argue that the reason behind Rivera’s inclusion of the portrait of Vladimir Lenin lies in his political and ideological commitment as well as his aesthetic project of achieving a link between his ideals and his artistic creations. His art reflected his vision of a world in which capitalism would be overcome and the proletariat held the main role in this transformation.

As a whole, in the case of Rivera, it is impossible to detach the aesthetic project from the political one. They are both intertwined, given the fact that the artist wanted to represent, through a fresco mural, the advantages and the utility of science, technology, and industry, for revolution. In a bipolar world, he confronted socialism and capitalism as two worldviews that needed to overcome obstacles in order to realize a just and classless society in the process of reaching communism. The aesthetic project was highly interfered with by his need to assert his *Leninism* and not lose his integrity as a valid artist. His depiction was in line with the request done by the Rockefellers, which concerned man as a builder, but the issue here was that the industrial assets and the context were used by Rivera as the justification for the existence of communism.

The clash between Rivera and the Rockefeller family

To understand the reason for Rivera’s appointment for such a demanding mission, it is significant to comprehend that in the artist’s previous works, such as the mural he painted in 1932 for the Detroit Institute of Art, he had reflected his great engagement with the evolution of technology and the interaction between science, technology, and the human life that the United States provided⁵³. “*Rivera was fascinated with the industrial might of the United States. Then, as now, there were voices who told of the corrupting force that the machine had loosed in the lives of humankind, but Rivera’s was not among them. He saw the machine as potentially liberating for the masses*”⁵⁴. Therefore, we can assert that the artist had already proven to be interested in the same outlook that the Center aimed at portraying. By this token, industry and technology were instruments at the disposal of those who strived for the establishment of a more equal society. This

⁵⁰ Their interpretations are included in Laurance Hurlburt, *The Mexican Muralists in the United States*, (Albuquerque, University of New Mexico Press, 1987) and it is cited in Apel, "Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural".

⁵¹ Linsley, "Utopia will not be televised: Rivera at Rockefeller Center", 48.

⁵² *Ib.*, 59.

⁵³ Aguilar-Moreno and Erika Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*, (Santa Bárbara, California: Greenwood Publishing Group, 2011).

⁵⁴ Robert L. Scott, "Diego Rivera at Rockefeller Center: Fresco Painting and Rhetoric", *Western Journal of Speech Communication*, (1977): 70-82.

highlights the sense of revolution he would print in his work, but the Rockefellers wouldn't learn how far he would go until later on.

As a result, the controversy arose when, amid his work, architects and Nelson Rockefeller himself discovered that Diego Rivera had introduced the face of Vladimir Lenin. It has been stated that the original sketch and the final sample of *Man at the Crossroads* both included the depiction of Vladimir Lenin; in such analysis, the figure of Lenin was less defined, for which his later clear representation is attributed to the growth in strength of the artist's conception of the leader⁵⁵. At the same time, after Raymond Hood, architect in charge of the Rockefeller Center building in New York had contacted Rivera in November 1932 and commissioned him to produce the mural, the artist proposed to represent mankind owing to the forces of nature, illustrated with the utility of electricity, and the right side of the painting showing workers having finally understood the significance of having rights⁵⁶; although such a description doesn't show at the first glance any sight of Vladimir Lenin, it does provide an understanding of the world vision held by Rivera. This detailed description could not have escaped the considerations of the Rockefeller family.

Alongside this notion, and taking into consideration the previously analyzed memorandum written by George Vincent in 1932⁵⁷, it is possible to assert that Diego Rivera surely abided by the premise set by the Rockefeller family in terms of presenting the opposition between past and present, given the fact that, even in times in which the opposition between capitalism and socialism as the causes for the creation of a bipolar world were yet nowhere in sight, he offered his representation of a capitalist world being overcome by the installment of a socialist system, as a clear manifestation of Marxist ideology. At the same time, in point e of the aforementioned document, Vincent had emphasized that "*some ideas involve controversy (Capital and Labor, International Peace, etc.). It would be unfortunate to attempt representations which might be open to doubt or even ridicule. It seems sound policy to adhere to objective depictions rather than to attempt idealistic symbolism*"⁵⁸. We can't assert with any assurance that Vincent was thinking about Rivera at this point, but the public was well aware of the artist's previous controversies. In those circumstances, the artist had been questioned for being "leftist", as well as for his disputable attitude. Is it possible to believe that Vincent was a visionary, and already was ahead of the events by fearing that some ideas like "capital" could generate problems in the conclusion of the work? It is undeniable that somebody who was so involved with the Rockefellers and had connections to the artistic world, could not have been oblivious to such public matters. In a letter from Nelson Rockefeller to Diego Rivera dated May 4th, 1933, the businessman regards the artist's work as thrilling but does not appreciate the inclusion of Lenin as it might offend a lot of people. The reasons

⁵⁵ "Lenin's Head: The Storm Center", *Workers Age*, June 15th, 1933.

⁵⁶ Such ideas are included in Irene Herner De Larrea et al., eds. *Diego Rivera: Paradise Lost at Rockefeller Center* (Mexico City: Edicupes, 1987), cited by A.K. Thompson, "Matter's Most Modern Configurations: Rivera, Picasso, and Benjamin's Dialectic Image", *Scapegoat*, (2013): 2-5.

⁵⁷ Memorandum by George Vincent, March 1932, Rockefeller Archive Center, <https://storage.rockarch.org/a3458647-f426-46e3-8806-e3ca452e5d1f-5dc488af6eab4abdb2ded6bfa6b50cac.pdf>, (accessed on June 2020)

⁵⁸ *Ib.*

behind his objection are the fact that it consists of a public building, and he even asserts that if it were a private one it would be of no inconvenience. He asks Rivera to replace the face with one of an unknown man and expects that the artist will understand and therefore make the suggested modifications⁵⁹. Rivera replied on May 6th that the inclusion had been present in the sketches sent to Raymond Hood, “*as a general and abstract representation of the concept of leader, an indispensable human figure*”⁶⁰.

According to Pliego Quijano, Rivera’s explanations caused that the Rockefeller family gave major relevance to the painting’s content, and such analysis revealed that indeed his bet was on the portrayal of socialism as the future for mankind⁶¹. On May 9th executive manager Hugh S. Robertson wrote a formal letter to Rivera stating that the sketch had no advance whatsoever on his final work, accusing him of taking advantage of a situation. The artist was given an ultimatum, and once he did not agree to change the painting, he was given the full payment of \$21.500 and escorted out⁶².

Communist demonstrators protested in the streets outside the building, asking to save Rivera’s work, mostly *Trotskyists* and several socialist and anarchist associations which later formed a committee to defend Rivera⁶³. Records of the destroyed painting are accessible merit of his assistant Lucienne Bloch, a talented photographer who entered the building incognito and took photos of the large mural and close-ups of Lenin’s face⁶⁴. Meanwhile, Nelson Rockefeller had no interest in seeing the painting destroyed; on the contrary, he wanted it to be removed and installed in the MoMA. However, this was impossible and in February 1934 the workmen chipped the painting from the wall, and Rockefeller and Rivera’s friendship was put to a stop for a few years⁶⁵. Added to this last fact, as proof that Nelson Rockefeller did not have an aversion for Rivera’s work is that even after the clash, he was yet more inclined toward Mexican art than before, traveling to the Maya ruins and diving into Pre-Columbian art⁶⁶.

The final decision to destroy the mural belonged to the architect and board of Todd Engineering Corporations, managers of the Rockefeller Center development, and John D. Rockefeller Jr. himself, all of which were responsible for Rivera’s dismissal⁶⁷. In a public statement dated May 19th, 1933, from the Office of John D. Rockefeller Jr., it is declared there was a “misunderstanding” that led to the disagreement between Diego Rivera and the authorities of the Rockefeller Center. The statement is very careful not to question Rivera’s fame or the bond that links him to the family, given that he “*has enjoyed the friendship and patronage of the*

⁵⁹ Nelson Rockefeller to Diego Rivera, May 4th, 1933, Rockefeller Center Archive, extracted from <https://www.christies.com/features/Lot-424-Diego-Rivera-The-Rivals-9011-6.aspx>

⁶⁰ Aguilar-Moreno and Cabrera, *Diego Rivera: A Biography*, 61.

⁶¹ Susana Pliego Quijano, *The man at the crossroads: Diego Rivera's mural at the Rockefeller Center*, (México: Trilce Ediciones, 2013).

⁶² *Ib.*

⁶³ Apel, "Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural".

⁶⁴ James C. Harris, "Diego Rivera’s Man at the Crossroads", *Archives of General Psychiatry*, (2012): 337-338.

⁶⁵ Morris, *Nelson Rockefeller: A Biography*.

⁶⁶ Pillsbury, "The Pan-American: Nelson Rockefeller and the Arts of Ancient Latin America".

⁶⁷ Harris, "Diego Rivera’s Man at the Crossroads".

Rockefeller family”⁶⁸. But there is a very interesting question they make which resumes the whole picture of the discord: *“In a decorative scheme, shall an artist be permitted to follow his own fancy, or shall he work in harmony with the project as planned?”*⁶⁹. This was definitely the issue for the Rockefeller Center and its representatives: Rivera didn’t respect the unity of the project, intending to portray an idea which wasn’t in conjunction with what had been agreed upon. But at the same time, it reflects the notion that the main problem was the representation of a communist figure. However, the sketch had already shown a world where capitalism was opposed to socialism, and Lenin was only the epitome of an evident and portrayed fact.

On October 10th, 1932, as the statement alludes, the Center had stated that three foreign artists –Frank Brangwyn from England, Diego Rivera from Mexico, and Sert from Spain –would be in charge to paint the nine panels for the main corridor of the 70-story business building of Rockefeller Center. Rivera would occupy the *“most prominent place, opposite the main entrance. The three artists were to work together in producing a unified decorative theme, of conservative character, suitable for such a structure”*⁷⁰. Sert would express man’s new mystery of the material world, Brangwyn would dedicate to the man’s new relationship with society and fellows, and Rivera would represent the man at the crossroads seeking a brighter future. The first two had performed according to the subject matter, unlike Rivera, who had definitely moved away from the original plan, after having stated that his work was red propaganda and considering himself not only a chosen artist but a perpetuator of the doctrines of Communism⁷¹. The issue here is that the discrepancy lies in the vision of future; the one imagined and illustrated by Rivera was not the one widely accepted by the United States society of the time. A future characterized by communism was not the norm but the exception, and an exception that the Rockefeller Center or society as a whole was not willing to acknowledge.

However, the statement is very careful in trying to depart from that idea. *“In the United States, personal opinion is free and untrammelled. There is no censorship of the press, and communist may legally nominate their leaders and vote for them in city, country, state and national elections. An artist may profess whatever doctrine he favors, but he cannot expect to use his work as a means of propaganda, when he is engaged to do something else. Murals such as those Rivera prepared for Rockefeller Center would have produced a storm of criticism”*⁷². Also, in order not to be related to a notion of censorship, it expresses that *“other than communist propaganda there are many objections to the mural the details of which have not been given to the public”*⁷³. But according to Nelson Rockefeller in the previously mentioned letter to Diego Rivera, his objection was to the image of Vladimir Lenin itself. Why doesn’t the statement mention which are the other

⁶⁸ “Sr. Rivera’s Mural”, New York (SIPA), May 19th, 1933, page 1 from Office of John D. Rockefeller Jr., Rockefeller Center Archive, <https://storage.rockarch.org/a3458647-f426-46e3-8806-e3ca452e5d1f-5dc488af6eab4abdb2ded6bfa6b50cac.pdf>, (accessed on June 2020)

⁶⁹ *Ib.*, 1.

⁷⁰ *Ib.*, 2.

⁷¹ *Ib.*

⁷² *Ib.*, 2-3.

⁷³ *Ib.*, 3.

objections that were supposedly made to the artwork? It is evident that once they figured out the piece depicted the opposition between the communist and the capitalist worlds, they decided Rivera's work was profane.

Most scholars hold the article *Rivera perpetuates scenes of communist activity for R.C.A. Walls – and Rockefeller, Jr., Foots Bill*, written by Joseph Lilly for the World-Telegram on April 24th of 1933 as responsible for launching the public controversy, particularly because ten days later Nelson Rockefeller wrote the infamous letter to Rivera⁷⁴. “Numerous articles as well as editorials appeared in *The New York Times* during the controversy, which began in the spring of 1933 and continued through the winter of 1934, when the mural was destroyed. The controversy was also given extensive coverage in the major art publications of the United States”⁷⁵.

According to the article *Rivera in Hot Water* of May 27th, 1933, in the replying letter to Rockefeller, Rivera also stated that if certain people were to be offended by the portrait of Lenin, “a deceased great man”, they would probably also be upset by his entire painting⁷⁶. Therefore, we can state that the image of Lenin was the tip of the ideological iceberg. Analyzing his words, we can comprehend that the primary sketch did not depart at all from the final drawings on the wall which never saw the light of day. It seems unlikely that neither Nelson Rockefeller nor his advisors were oblivious to the implicit and non-implicit messages in the picture, as well as in Rivera's entire muralist works. He had already been engaged in controversies before this debacle, he had faced severe criticism and scandals in Mexico, and he had written essays regarding his ideological stand and the use of art for such propaganda.

Not only did Rockefeller seem to have believed he would avoid political controversies, but his own advisors invited Rivera with misconceptions about his ideological viewpoints. One of the family's purchasing agents, Frances Flynn Paine, who had followed mural commissions for Rivera and who was responsible for his arrival in the United States⁷⁷, added to the mistaken notions of the meaning of Rivera's work. “*Diego's very spinal column is painting, not politics. Every inclination of his life has led to painting. The political movement interested him because it was to him a vital part of contemporary life. We are living in a time of intensive upheaval and reconstruction*”⁷⁸. Paine attributed Rivera's participation in the Communist Party as a mere means in his process of fulfillment as an artist. But the fact that Rivera forcefully averted from the Party in no way implies he put his ideological standpoints aside. However, as stated by Servando Ortoll, Paine was the person who defined Rivera as the strongest “red” in Latin America to the Rockefellers⁷⁹; we assume that in

⁷⁴ Apel, “Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural”.

⁷⁵ Quirarte, “Mexican and Mexican American Artists in the United States: 1920-1970”, 26.

⁷⁶ “Rivera in Hot Water”, *Literary Digest*, May 27th 1933.

⁷⁷ Anna Indych-López, “Mural Gambits: Mexican Muralism in the United States and the “Portable” Fresco”, *The Art Bulletin*, (2007): 287-305.

⁷⁸ Frances Flynn Paine, “The work of Diego Rivera”, in *The work of Diego Rivera*, (New York: Museum of Modern Art; W.W. Norton & Company, Inc., 1931), 35.

⁷⁹ Servando Ortoll, “Diego Rivera, José María Sert, y los Rockefeller: una historia con cuatro epílogos”, *Journal of Iberian and Latin American Studies*, (2004): 1-22.

his somewhat naïve conception of Rivera's art, he believed the artist would be capable of detaching his personal beliefs from his aesthetic product.

At the same time, in the early 1920s, the United States had experienced a phase of fear of the intrusion of socialism as a result of the Russian Revolution of 1917, known as the *Red Scare*⁸⁰, which also added to such refusal of the Rockefellers to have an art piece in their Center which included the figure of Lenin. This brings us back to the interrogative of their integration of Rivera in the project considering that his participation in other projects in the U.S. had been controversial so far and his writings up to that moment were very much clear regarding his ideological stance. That is why Rivera asserted that *"Those who gave me the work at Radio City knew perfectly well my artistic tendencies and my social and political opinions. And the Detroit affair had just served to make very clear the nature of my reaction to the environment of the United States"*⁸¹.

Therefore, it cannot be assured that Nelson Rockefeller had not foreseen Rivera's intentions; at the least, it could be stated that Rivera embodied his rebellious side, and once he found it was an impossibility to continue with the artist as a result of family and business pressures, he attributed the guilt of the debacle to Rivera's inclusion of Lenin. All at once, what the artist represents does not always become clear to someone who is not immersed in the artistic world, even for people like Nelson Rockefeller and his mother who had been strong advocates of Latin American art. After all, their concern could be considered as a part of business entrepreneurship, for which their main task was not to handle the political meanings behind an art piece, but the aesthetic one, in terms of whether the paintings visually matched their purposes for the Center. More scandalous assertions even refer to an inducement from the Rockefellers themselves. *"According to Hurlburt, it was the Rockefellers, in particular Abigail Aldrich Rockefeller, who encouraged Rivera to include Lenin's portrait in the notorious Rockefeller Center mural"*⁸². However, we don't really hold evidence of such an assumption. What has been argued is that she was sturdily aware of Rivera's political preferences, given she had purchased the sketchbook he had produced in his years spent in the Soviet Union⁸³.

After the controversy reached its higher point, Rivera referred to art developed in line with proletariat struggle, specifying that his goal was –the same way he did in Mexico the former years– to execute such kind of art for the workers of the United States. Thus, this had been his main motivation to accept the various offers he had received in the North American country. He also pointed out how, after repeatedly praising his work, Nelson Rockefeller had finally felt unease by the portrayal of Lenin which, from the start on, had been present in the sketches as well as on the wall for a whole month; at the same time, he stressed that a crowd of architects had complained not only about the presence of Lenin's face, but also the entire spirit of the painting. As a result,

⁸⁰ Julie Crew, "Men at the Crossroads: The unlikely partnership of Diego Rivera and the Rockefellers", *Undergraduate Research Journal of History*, (2017): 35-43.

⁸¹ Diego Rivera, "The Radio City Mural", *Workers Age*, June 15th, 1933.

⁸² Nieto, "The Mexican presence in the United States: part I", 34.

⁸³ Such an idea is included in Wendy Jeffers, "Abby Aldrich Rockefeller Patron of the Modern", *Magazine Antiques*, 166, no.5 (November 2004), cited in Crew, "Men at the Crossroads: The unlikely partnership of Diego Rivera and the Rockefellers".

he referred to the Rockefellers as a “financial dictatorship”⁸⁴. Thus, we can grasp the notion that Rivera’s revolutionary socialist purposes were always present, joint with his aesthetic project.

Rivera blamed the Rockefeller-controlled newspapers which damaged the reputation of the art piece, trying to make it seem like he added the head a posteriori⁸⁵. The real issue revolved around the vision of the future, given that “*With the affair of the Rivera mural, the Rockefellers and their associates in the Center, including above all David Sarnoff, realized that the theme ‘Man at the Crossroads’ was an open invitation to contest the future of technology. Rivera’s socialist vision of a future in which technical progress is inextricably bonded to social change was incompatible with the ambitions of businessmen who wanted to exploit technology within capitalism*”⁸⁶.

After the destruction of the mural, the Mexican government permitted Rivera to recreate it in the Palace of Fine Arts in Mexico City where it is placed nowadays, in which he triumphantly added portraits of other historical figures such as Trotsky, Marx, and Engels in the socialist side, and quite sarcastically, that of John D. Rockefeller Jr. in the capitalist side. He also changed the name of the mural to *Man, controller of the Universe*⁸⁷. The controversy was illustrative of the political convictions of the artist, and it placed on the table the debate on whether art can be used for propaganda and political struggle; nonetheless, the mission was accomplished, because it proved how socialism had to fight the principles of capitalism and how art was a powerful means of communication⁸⁸. It must be added that, to the benefit of the Rockefellers, it was such a heated topic in the mass media for weeks that their Rockefeller Center project consisted of not only a business scheme but also a cultural one. Whether it was negative or positive publicity, it was publicity nonetheless; and considering the U.S. society of the 1930s, most condemnations must have been targeted at Diego Rivera.

Conclusion

The ideas put forward in this essay can shed light on the specifics of the conflict between Diego Rivera and the Rockefeller family in 1933 concerning the painting *Man at the Crossroads*. If we think about the Rockefellers as a symbol of the American economy and their involvement in cultural ventures and their contribution to the influence that the United States wanted to maintain throughout the Latin American region, we can understand what their goals were. They aimed to create works of art that portrayed the importance of technology and communication –given their involvement in the development of television– and the role of men as important contributors to these advances. Diego Rivera's art, although controversial since his arrival in the United States, reflected these elements, and at the same time, he was one of the most appreciated artists in the wave of Mexican *muralism*.

⁸⁴ Diego Rivera, "The Radio City Mural", *Workers Age*, June 15th, 1933.

⁸⁵ *Ib.*

⁸⁶ Linsley, "Utopia will not be televised: Rivera at Rockefeller Center", 58.

⁸⁷ Apel, "Diego Rivera and the Left: the destruction and the recreation of the Rockefeller Center Mural".

⁸⁸ Pliego Quijano, *The man at the crossroads: Diego Rivera's mural at the Rockefeller Center*.

What is relevant, however, is that there were also conflicting interests within the Rockefeller family: on the one hand, Rockefeller Jr. was not particularly taken with Rivera's art and would have much preferred the presence of European artists, as reflected in correspondence with his advisors; on the other hand, his son Nelson and his wife Abby seemed much more interested in Rivera's work, especially given their developed interest in Latin American art, which would continue in subsequent years. Diego Rivera proved to be consistent with the Rockefeller vision of a world dominated by technology, science, and industry. However, as a man who remained true to his political convictions and refused to give up his artistic integrity, one can understand that conflict was inevitable. Especially because Rivera had to face a two-front struggle –with both the right and the left– because he not only had to prove his artistic ability but also reaffirm his ideological point of view. Importantly, it seems he always intended to remain true to his convictions, because even if his somewhat conciliatory attitude made him put technology and big business at the service of the fight against capitalism, he continued to profess his communism outside the Mexican Communist Party.

The Rockefellers and their advisors took a somewhat innocent viewpoint in believing that the artist could separate the aesthetic project from the political: the political commitment is always linked to the artistic representation, because just as a historian writes with his own background in mind, the artist always has a goal to show, a purpose to paint. What clashed between the two sides above all was the vision of the future they represented: Rivera saw a future society grounded in communism, while the Rockefellers extolled the benefits of capitalism. By and large, both were serving their own personal interests.

It cannot be said that the Rockefellers were not warned of Rivera's intent: although Lenin's head is not clearly visible in the original sketch, his description of what it would represent already contained elements that revealed his ideological position, and the sketch already showed a dual reality that could be embedded in the ideas of capitalism and communism. Even if they justified the destruction by saying that there were many other objections to the mural, the problem was really Lenin's face, which could be understood in the context of the fear of the invasion of communism in the country.

However, it is interesting to note how long the media discussed this matter, which actually proved beneficial for the publicity of the Rockefeller City project as well as for the figure of Diego Rivera as a prominent artist. The controversy underscored the family's relevance in the economic and cultural arena of the United States and demonstrated that it was no stranger to controversy. It also confirmed Rivera's ideological convictions and his contentious character. The fact that the friendship between Nelson Rockefeller and the artist was resumed in the following years proves that the clash was not only an artistic confrontation but also a divergence in world political visions.

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